

FORMS AND METHODS OF EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Basic phrases and terms: education, methods of education, types of education methods, methods that serve to form social consciousness, methods of habituation and training in activities, methods of encouragement and punishment in education.

1. Understanding of educational methods.

The categories of purpose, content, and form reveal the essence of the educational process (what it is aimed at, what it fills, what it is directed to, and how it is completed). However, there is another important category related to the question of how to educate in the clarification of the essence of education. This is the concept of education method. The method of education (from the Greek "methodos" - the way) is the way to achieve the goal of education. When applied to school practice, methods are methods of influencing the mind, will, feelings and behavior of students.

No educator is capable of creating completely new methods of education. The problem of improving the methods is always present, each educator solves it according to his ability, enriches the general methodology based on the expression of his private views in accordance with the specific conditions of the educational process. Such private improvement of educational methods is called educational methods. Educational methods are a part of the general method, a separate action, further definition. Figuratively speaking, methods are an unexplored path that an educator paves the way with his students in order to achieve the set goal faster. If other educators start to use it, then gradually the methods can turn into broad-based ways - methods. Knowing educational methods and methods, mastering the ability to use them correctly is one of the important characteristics that determine the level of pedagogical skills. That is the relevance of educational methods and methods.

In practice, the concept of educational tools is also distinguished. Methods mean a unit of influence, and a tool means a set of methods. A tool is neither a method nor a method. For example, work is a means of education, but showing it, evaluating work, showing mistakes in work are methods. Words (in a broad sense) are educational tools, but analogies are methods. In this connection, educational methods are sometimes defined as a system of methods and tools used for the successful implementation of a set goal. Also, methods and tools will definitely be present in the structure of the method.

2. Purpose and content of educational methods

There are no pros and cons of the method, it is impossible to evaluate a certain way in the process of education as highly effective or ineffective. The effectiveness of the method can be evaluated from the point of view of the conditions in which it is used.

Appropriate selection of educational methods depends on a number of factors.

1. Goals and tasks of education. The goal not only justifies the methods, but also defines them. Whatever the goal, the methods of achieving it must be in accordance with it.

2. Content of education. Do not forget that the same task can be filled with different ideas. Therefore, it is very important to connect the methods not with the content at all, but with a clear idea.

3. Taking into account the age characteristics of the students. This or similar tasks are solved depending on the age of the students. Age is not simply a numerical indicator of how long one has lived. It reflects the acquired social experience, the level of development of psychological and moral qualities. For example, the sense of responsibility can be formed in students studying in primary education, secondary education and secondary special, vocational education institutions. However, different methods are used for the formation of this quality at each stage.

4. The level of formation of the team. In connection with the development of the collective form of self-management, the methods of pedagogical influence do not remain unchanged. As we know, the flexibility of management is a necessary condition for the successful cooperation of the educator with the students.

5. Individual characteristics of students. General methods, general programs cannot be the basis of educational interaction. It is necessary to adjust them individually and personally. A humanistic pedagogue tries to use methods that allow each person to develop his own identity, to preserve his own identity, to realize his "I".

6. Educational conditions. It includes material, psychophysiological, sanitary-hygienic relations in the classroom: the climate in the team, the method of pedagogical leadership, etc. It is known that there are no abstract conditions, they are always concrete. Their combination is visible in certain cases. Pedagogical situations are the conditions in which education takes place.

7. Educational tools. Educational methods are formed from educational tools that appear as components of the educational process. There are other educational tools that are closely related to the methods and are used together. For example, visual aids, visual arts and music, mass media that provide necessary support for the effective application of methods.

8. Level of pedagogical qualification. The educator usually chooses only the methods that he knows and has learned to use. Many methods are complex and require a lot of effort on the part of the teacher. Educators who avoid such responsibility try to organize activities without them. As a result, it is less effective than using methods based on different images, different goals, tasks, and conditions.

9. Education time. When there is little time and the goal is great, "strong moving" methods are used, and in favorable conditions, "sparing" methods of education are used. It is necessary to divide education into "strongly moving" and "sparing" methods: the first one is connected with reprimanding and coercion, and the second one is connected with exhortation and constant training.

10. Expected result. When choosing a method, the educator must be confident that he will succeed. For this, it is necessary to know in advance what the method used will lead to.

3. Classification of educational methods

In modern pedagogy, there are dozens of classifications of education, some of which focus on solving practical tasks, and some of which reflect only theoretical tasks.

Methods are divided into persuasion, training, encouragement and reprimand according to their specific character. In this case, the general characteristic of the method reflects its orientation, originality, applicability. The general methods of education, which are distinguished by the more generalization of the methods, are firmly connected to this classification. It includes methods of persuasion, organization of activities, motivation of students' behavior. I.S. In Marenko's classification, groups of educational methods are named as follows: explanatory-

reproductive, problem-based, teaching and training methods, motivational, obstructive, management, self-education.

Methods can be divided into two groups according to the results of their impact on students:

1. Ethical standards that influence the formation of motives, the formation of imagination, understanding, and ideas.
2. Affecting the formation of habits that determine one or another type of behavior.

Methods depend on the purpose and content of education. The methods of education are aimed at developing the qualities of a well-rounded person. Therefore, taking into account the level of development of students is an important condition for the effective use of educational methods.

Pupils react differently to this or that educational influence. It depends on their special characteristics, the level of upbringing, the extent to which educational methods are chosen appropriately and effectively, and how skillfully they are used. The correct choice of educational methods helps to increase the activity of self-education of students in solving educational tasks positively. For example, in the process of working with first-grade students, the teacher uses the method of explaining to them the rules of behavior of students, the importance of having a clear agenda, and the need for students to follow a strict order when teaching students new work activities. In addition to explaining, he trains them to enter the classroom correctly, to greet the teacher and students, and to maintain discipline. At the same time, the students of the first grade are used to the above processes during the lesson. In this process, the positive work they have done, the results of their educational work, require encouragement. It can be seen that the teacher uses different methods and methods when conducting the educational process with students. The variety of educational methods shows the need to divide and classify them into types. Therefore, they can be divided into groups, taking into account their special characteristics. Every teacher (educator) who wants to achieve educational results should thoroughly master educational methods and their essence.

Figure 1.

The task of the first group of methods is to create an understanding and knowledge of the social consciousness of the student about the rules and norms of life, ethics, labor relations. In the process of education, these rules and norms become the beliefs, confidence and life views of a person. This group includes spiritual, moral, aesthetic, ideological, legal, physical, ecological, economic, etc. content conversations and modeling techniques can be included. With the help of the methods of the second group, the student forms habits related to spiritual content. The behavior of the student is formed in accordance with the content of social education on the basis of moral habits and on the ground of activity. Activity is an important resource that enriches the experience of social relations and social behavior of students. Among the methods of the second group, the method of pedagogical demand is important. Pedagogical demand can be the fulfillment of various tasks, i.e. expressing the norms of social behavior, performing a specific task that needs to be performed by participating in this or that activity, and encouraging one or another action. Claims can be made directly or indirectly. Direct requirements are in the form of a strict command or instruction, a task, a guiding description. Indirect demands are expressed in the form of advice, request, rebuke, interest in activities, with the aim of arousing a sense of experience and aspiration. Requirements imply that the student has some level of awareness, reason, purpose, and belief. At the same time, the teacher must pay special attention to the

standards of the requirements imposed on the students. In the process of useful activities and specially organized tasks, positive behavior and characters are taught. Teaching is an activity that motivates students to perform various actions and practical activities organized in a planned and systematic manner in order to transform social behavior into a normal form.

Teaching is considered an effective tool at all stages of education and development of students. Exercises in the activity are aimed at training the habits of work, social activity, team activity and interaction. Training is closely related to teaching. If the basis of teaching lies in the child's mastery of the activity process, then the activity of training is of special importance for the individual. Training relies heavily on learning to control repetition, reinforcement, and improvement, which increasingly become the basis of social behavior.

In educational practice, it is often necessary to create special pedagogical situations, in which there is an opportunity for independent choice. Pedagogical situations create conditions where students have to change their thoughts and behavior again. Among the methods of the second group, the competition is a necessary and important quality of increasing the efficiency of the methods of organizing students' practical activities. The competition helps to develop students' activity and creativity in all spheres of activity, and to direct the activity of the student team to a specific goal. When the competition is organized correctly, the feeling of the team is successfully formed, and the discipline and organization of the students are strengthened. The competition is organized by specific type, as well as systematically: for example, the best class, the best group, the best team, the best school, etc. In the process of education, it is important to achieve that the students organize the competition based on their own initiative and enthusiasm, develop its conditions and indicators. It is also necessary to take care of the overall success of the team, the fulfillment of the accepted obligation, and ensuring that the results of the competition are reflected in the stands. It is inappropriate to organize the competition for official information. Public opinion remains an important basis of competition activity.

Consciousness and behavior unity occurs through the interdependent use of the first and second group methods, but this does not happen by itself, but depends on the teacher's organizational skills and his ability to see the features and importance of tools that affect the student's mind and behavior. In a word, as a result of education, today's student becomes a perfect person, that is, a perfect member of society. For this, he should develop his mind and thinking and form positive qualities in himself. So, what level of activity should the human mind reach in order to understand existence and the environment?

Human consciousness is the level of spiritual perspective activity based on understanding of life and worldly reality through his perception and reason. Reason is to understand worldly and life truths based on one's own perception, heart and mind and to follow them in one's activities from a spiritual and human point of view.

The methods of the third group include methods that are used to stimulate positive behavior in students, correct or prevent negative traits, and directly influence their feelings and goals. This group includes methods such as incentives and punishments.

4. Role of example in education

The role of good education in the family and society is incomparable in the development of our children into perfect human beings in the future. The more cultured and polite the parents, mentors, leaders and adults are, the more polite the people growing up in this society and environment will be. It is an urgent issue today to carry out social work with such responsibility, that is, to be a good example and role model for our youth so that they grow up to be polite,

well-behaved and conscientious people. There was a saying in the old days: "Do what the teacher says, don't do what he does." Now this adage is outdated: teenagers and young adults often take an example from the external lifestyle of their teachers and adults, that is, they "do what the teacher does". At this point, it is necessary to take into account their rightful objections: "Why do they tell you not to smoke and drink, when they themselves smoke and drink?", "Why do they tell you to tell the truth, but they themselves tell lies?" They say you have to be honest, but they take bribes themselves?" If a teacher and others are right in words and wrong in practice, how will their students respect them? What do they learn from him? In this sense, the educator must always follow his word and go beyond his word. It is this aspect of Ibrat that is of great importance in the education of a perfect person.

Ibrat education has interested people since ancient times. This is especially common in the pandnoms associated with the names of the famous Greek thinkers - Plato and Aristotle. In particular, in Eastern countries, Plato's admonitions to Arastu, Aristotle's admonitions to Alexander, and testaments were distributed as a whole work. Aristotle said that the educator should be educated and acquire human qualities. "Know that," says Aristotle, "a person engaged in education cannot educate others if he himself has not been educated." A good-natured person cannot start others into naughty and dirty deeds. If you want to train your student, first start by training your soul. If you want to eliminate the guilt of others, you must first cleanse yourself of defects and vices. But how can a blind person guide the blind? Can a lowly person give honor and dignity to others?"]

In addition to these, works such as "Rushnoinoma", "Nightmare", "Pandnoma" by Farididdin Attar, "Sad pand" by Obaid Zakoni are widely spread in Eastern countries. In the early Middle Ages, the treatises of Aristotle and his followers were translated into Arabic, and their teachings were studied and enriched by Al-Kindi, Al-Farabi, Beruni, Ibn Sina, Omar Khayyam, Nasriddin Tusi, Jami, Nawai and other Eastern philosophers.

Therefore, the role of role models is incomparable in the maturity of today's youth and the worldview corresponding to it is regularly improved and developed. This, in turn, guarantees the training of conscious members of the Free and Prosperous Motherland, creators of a free and prosperous life.

5. Methods of encouragement and punishment in education

Methods of encouragement - provide positive assessment of students' actions. Stimulation creates experiences of joy, satisfaction, satisfaction, gives refreshment and motivation, strengthens confidence in one's own strength, encourages positive behavior, increases responsibility for one's own work and behavior. Motivational techniques are varied and include approval, encouragement, encouragement, reassurance, notes, verbal and written appreciation, rewards, and more.

Stimulation should be applied taking into account pedagogical requirements. Any incentive should be commensurate with the student's true service to the team. At the time of promotion, special characteristics of the student, his position in the team should be taken into account and it should not be consecutive. Excessive praise, comparison in relation to the team, relaxation of demandingness, these cause the appearance of selfishness and selfishness in the student. In the organization of incentives, along with the student's success, it is necessary to take into account his place in the team, his moral image, as well as the opinion of the team regarding work, team assignments, and the team's attitude to itself. Punishment methods are negative evaluations of students' behavior and activities. Punishment refers to the discussion of activities

and behaviors that are contrary to moral standards. Punishment can prevent bad behavior, correct morals, shame in front of the community, and create a sense of guilt. There are also various methods of punishment by the team or on the basis of its support, including reprimanding, putting, shaming, blushing, discussion of behavior among the team, exclusion from certain activities, etc.

It is necessary to follow pedagogical requirements for punishment. The given punishment should be appropriate and should be given depending on the students' guilt and negative behavior. When punishing, it is necessary to take into account the causes of negative behavior, the harm it causes to the community, and the student's personal characteristics.

Punishment should not arise from the student's interests or serve him. Punishment can also be given by the team. In all cases, the student should not be physically and mentally tormented, humiliated, humiliated, or violated. It is appropriate to use educational methods taking into account the conditions, time, as well as their interaction with each other. Educational tools include the type of activity organized according to the purpose of education. Games, educational work, sports and other types of activities are such tools. In addition, various subjects, examples of material and spiritual culture, information and technical tools are also used as educational tools in the educational process. For example, visual and educational tools, artistic and scientific literature, works of art, radio, television, computer, tape recorder, slides, and people can serve as educational tools. The use of educational tools always requires the use of appropriate educational methods, because with their help, consciousness, emotions, and behavior are formed. Various activities of the student are organized. Today, special attention is paid to the use of information and technical means in the educational process. Appropriate and effective use of them leads to the spiritual growth of students.

Based on the above-mentioned considerations, the following conclusions can be drawn on the topic.

1. Since the basis of the educational process is formed by laws that reflect the objective requirements of social life, the social essence and nature of a person, conducting the educational process in a scientifically based manner requires a deep study of its laws.

2. The success of the educational process also depends on the principles of its organization. The principles of education are a set of basic ideas and rules that originate from the purpose of educating the young generation and define the most important requirements for the content, methods and direction of educating a perfect person.

3. The methods used by the teacher in the organization of the educational process are also important, and they are determined by the tasks of raising the young generation to become a well-rounded, free, creative, independent thinker, which is set before the educational institutions by the social society. Educational methods are divided into three groups according to their similarities. Educational tools used in the process of education serve to strengthen the importance of methods.

Concepts to remember:

Method is derived from the Latin word *metodos*, which means the concepts of research, theory, and doctrine. It is understood as a set of internal ways, methods, and tools typical of the real processes of teaching and upbringing.

Educational methods - method is derived from the Latin word *metodos* - road. The method is translated as research way, theory, teaching. As a scientific concept, the word "method" is understood in a broad sense as a way to achieve a specific goal.

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